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OCCLUSAL TRAUMA AND PERIODONTITIS

Veljovic T.¹, Đurić M.^{1,2}, Mirnić J.¹, Gušić I.^{1,2}, Maletin A.¹, Ramić B.¹, Vukoje K.¹

¹Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

²Clinic for Dentistry, Novi Sad, Serbia

Abstract: Occlusal trauma—defined as structural and functional changes in the periodontal tissues caused by excessive occlusal forces—may occur in a healthy or inflamed periodontium due to periodontal disease. The role of occlusal trauma in the initiation and progression of periodontal disease has been extensively studied. Despite conflicting findings, there is a general consensus that trauma caused by occlusion does not initiate gingivitis or periodontitis or accelerate the progression of gingivitis to periodontitis. Rather, both animal and human studies indicated that occlusal forces could be a co-factor in the progression of periodontal disease by changing the pathway and spread of inflammation into the deeper periodontal tissues. Occlusal therapy is an integral part of periodontal therapy and may be performed in different treatment phases.

Key words: Periodontitis, Occlusal trauma, Occlusal adjustment, Periodontal therapy

Introduction

As teeth and periodontium are constantly exposed to the occlusal forces generated by the orofacial system, periodontium can undergo physiological changes. Although periodontium can accommodate to the forces exerted on the tooth crown, its adaptive capacity varies among individuals, as well as across the lifespan of the same person [1].

Structural and functional changes in the periodontal tissues as a result of occlusal forces can lead to *occlusal trauma* [2] also known as traumatic occlusion, periodontal trauma, traumatogenic occlusion, trauma of occlusion, etc. [3]. The extent of these changes depends on the magnitude, direction, duration, and frequency of traumatic occlusal forces, and can lead to either primary or secondary occlusal trauma. *Primary occlusal trauma* results from excessive occlusal force applied to tooth or teeth supported by healthy and non-inflamed periodontium [4]. It can arise due to high restorations, the drifting or extrusion of teeth into spaces created by unreplaced missing teeth, and the orthodontic movement of teeth into functionally unacceptable positions. Trauma is considered primary if it is deemed the sole etiologic factor in periodontal destruction and if the local alteration to which a tooth is subjected is attributed to occlusion only. Moreover, as shown in Figure 1, changes produced by primary trauma do not alter the level of connective tissue attachment and do not initiate pocket formation [1]. This type of occlusal trauma does not affect the marginal gingiva and does not lead to an increase in gingival crevicular fluid [3]. *Secondary occlusal trauma*, on the other hand, refers to changes induced by normal or excessive occlusal forces in the attachment apparatus of a tooth or teeth with inadequate or functionally compromised supporting tissues (Figure 1) [4]. In these cases, periodontium becomes more vulnerable to injury, and previously well-tolerated occlusal forces become traumatic [1]. Although this type of trauma does not cause gingival inflammation or the formation of periodontal pockets, it may increase the risk of progression and severity of plaque-induced inflammation [5].

Figure 1. Primary and secondary occlusal trauma (Source: T.G. Wilson Jr. et al. *Advances in periodontics*, 1992).

Occlusal trauma can also be described as acute or chronic. *Acute occlusal trauma* occurs following an abrupt increase in occlusal load, such as that produced by biting too strongly on a hard object. It can also be induced by inappropriately designed restorations or prosthetic appliances, which would consequently interfere with or alter the direction of occlusal forces on the teeth. Acute trauma typically manifests as tooth pain, sensitivity to percussion, and increased tooth mobility. *Chronic occlusal trauma* occurs when abnormal occlusal forces are exerted on the tooth supporting structures for prolonged periods. As it is more common than acute trauma, it has greater clinical significance. If its causes are not eliminated, it can induce periodontal changes associated with gradual alteration in occlusion produced by tooth wear, movement, and extrusion, in combination with parafunctional habits (e.g., bruxism, clenching).

Occlusal trauma most commonly arises due to occlusal prematurity, whereby a particular tooth is inadequately aligned with the remaining dental arc, which prevents the harmonious closure of the jaw. This misbalance can result in damage to periodontium, masticatory muscles, and temporomandibular joint. Occlusal prematurity can be a direct result of missing teeth, caries or fracture, tooth abrasion, malposition, inadequate dental restoration, vertical dimension reduction and genetic factors. However, it can also be indirectly caused by apical periodontitis, periodontal diseases, tumors of the maxillofacial region, TMJ diseases and orthodontic tooth movement.

Effects of occlusal trauma on the initiation and progression of periodontitis

The relationship between occlusal trauma and periodontal disease has been a subject of extensive research, primarily involving animal experiments and clinical epidemiological studies. Stillman and other early investigators suggested that excessive occlusal force was the main cause of periodontitis [6,7,8], but this claim later proved to be controversial [5].

In the 1960s, Glickman described an alteration in the inflammation pathway as a result of occlusal trauma, positing that excessive occlusal forces could be a contributing factor in the progression of periodontal disease by allowing inflammation to progress into the deeper periodontal tissues, resulting in angular and crater-like bone loss [9, 10]. According to Glickman, the periodontal structures comprise of irritation and co-destruction zones. The zone of irritation includes the free gingiva (marginal and interdental gingival tissues), whereas the zone of co-destruction includes the periodontal ligament, root cementum, and alveolar bone. It is coronally demarcated by the transeptal and dentoalveolar collagen fibers of the gingival connective tissue. As shown in Figure 2, inflammatory lesion in the zone of irritation propagates into (1) periodontal ligament when teeth are subjected to trauma from occlusion and (2) alveolar bone when teeth are not subjected to occlusion

trauma. Glickman's pioneering work on this topic subsequently led to a series of animal experiments to investigate his findings.

Figure 2. Glickman's concept. A – zone of irritation, B – zone of co-destruction (Source: B. Shalu. *Periodontics Revisited*. 2011. 10.5005/jp/books/11320_28)

Owing to the animal studies conducted prior to the 1980s, subgingival biofilm was identified as the main risk factor for the development of periodontitis, the severity and progression of which was nonetheless still believed to be affected by occlusal trauma [11,12]. Human studies conducted in this period have also yielded conflicting findings. For example, a number of cross-sectional epidemiological studies failed to establish a relationship between premature tooth contact and increased probing depth or bone loss, while several authors reported an association of mobility and radiographic evidence of a widened periodontal ligament with increased pocket depth, attachment loss and bone loss [13]. For example, Nunn et al. noted that teeth with occlusal discrepancies had significantly deeper initial probing depths, greater mobility, and poorer prognoses than those without occlusal discrepancies [14]. These authors consequently concluded that occlusal discrepancy can be an independent risk factor contributing to periodontal disease. Based on their findings, Harrel et al. argued that multiple types of occlusal contacts—including premature contacts in centric relation, posterior protrusive contact, non-working contacts, combined working and non-working contacts—and the occlusal discrepancies between centric relation and centric occlusion were associated with significantly deeper probing depths and increased likelihood of unfavorable prognosis [15]. These authors further noted that, at 1-year follow-up, the chance of a deteriorating periodontal situation was 60% lower in teeth without premature contacts at initial examination, as well as in teeth where premature contacts had been eliminated. These findings are encouraging, as they indicate that occlusal treatment can be an important adjunct therapy in the comprehensive treatment of periodontal disease [16].

Although occlusion trauma is reversible, as the affected tissues undergo repair following the removal of traumatic force, its effects may not always be temporary and can have long-lasting clinical significance. The presence of inflammation in the periodontium as a result of plaque accumulation, in particular, may compromise adequate resolution of traumatic lesions.

Clinical and Radiographic Signs of Occlusal Trauma

Occlusal trauma primarily manifests as increased tooth mobility due to the destruction of the periodontal fibers and enlargement of the periodontal ligament space, which can be accompanied by tooth drifting, tooth abrasion, occlusal discrepancies, tooth fracture, fremitus, tooth migration (especially in frontal teeth), sensitivity to thermal stimuli, discomfort and pain, and gingival recessions [3]. Radiographic examination may further reveal increased periodontal ligament space width, radiolucency and condensation of alveolar bone, discontinuity and thickening of lamina dura, angular bony defects, and root resorption [13].

Occlusal adjustment

Occlusal therapy is an integral part of periodontal therapy and can hinder the progression of periodontal disease, thereby improving the overall prognosis. Its primary aim is to alleviate the etiological factors and ensure comfortable and functional dentition, which requires accomplishment of several therapeutic objectives:

1. Elimination or reduction of tooth mobility
2. Establishment or maintenance of a stable, reproducible intercuspal position
3. Ensuring freedom of movement to and from the intercuspal position, including movement in all directions regardless of the initial point of contact
4. Ensuring efficient masticatory function
5. Achieving comfortable occlusion
6. Establishing occlusion that would provide acceptable phonation and esthetics
7. Eliminating or modifying parafunctional habits [17]

Treatment considerations for patients with occlusal traumatism that have developed chronic periodontitis may include one or more of the following options:

1. Selective tooth grinding
2. Prosthetic therapy
3. Orthodontic tooth movement
4. Splinting
5. Extraction of selected teeth

Selective grinding (coronoplasty) involves precisely altering the occlusal surfaces of certain teeth to improve the overall contact pattern. Since this procedure is irreversible and involves the removal of tooth structure, it is of limited usefulness. Even when proper indications exist, coronoplasty should be performed only after inflammation surrounding the tooth has been adequately controlled, because tooth can be in supraocclusion as a consequence of inflammation. If coronoplasty is performed first, once inflammation has been treated, the affected tooth will be in infraocclusion. In general, selective grinding is appropriate only when the required alterations do not extend beyond the enamel structure. If this is not possible, and enamel has been penetrated by selective grinding, proper restorative procedures must be used. In patients with a large number of missing teeth, chewing forces are concentrated on the remaining teeth. In such cases, selective grinding is contraindicated and should be replaced by prosthetic therapy.

Occlusal therapy may also be performed as a part of orthodontic treatment, especially in different types of rough malocclusion. Tooth repositioning by applying appropriate orthodontic forces is one of the most widely used treatments following occlusion trauma. Still, this treatment modality is not without its drawbacks. For example, a periodontally compromised tooth with little bone support is not a good candidate for orthodontic tooth movement. Similarly, it is not advisable to move the tooth to a position which will further compromise its stability and long-term prognosis. In other words, the primary goal of orthodontic force application is tooth movement that will eliminate abnormal occlusal forces as well as improve long-term prognosis.

Periodontal splints can also be used to maintain and stabilize mobile teeth in their functional position and should be applied:

- To stabilize increasingly mobile teeth that have not responded to occlusal adjustment and periodontal treatment
- To prevent tipping or drifting and the over-eruption of unopposed teeth
- To stabilize teeth after orthodontic treatment
- To stabilize teeth following acute trauma

In rare cases, occlusal trauma may require tooth extraction, especially if the target tooth exhibits extensive periodontal involvement with poor prognosis, or when its removal would improve

the prognosis of the remaining teeth. Extraction of certain teeth may also be warranted to achieve more optimal position and alignment of the remaining teeth.

Occlusal therapy may be performed in different treatment phases, but is usually preceded by efforts to reduce or minimize inflammatory lesions. Evaluation of occlusal symptoms should continue throughout the course of therapy.

Conclusion

Available scientific evidence does not support the view that trauma from occlusion causes gingivitis or periodontitis, or accelerates the progression of gingivitis to periodontitis. Rather, extant research suggests that occlusal forces could contribute to the progression of periodontal disease by changing the pathway and spread of inflammation into the deeper periodontal tissues. Trauma from occlusion when combined with inflammation can produce infrabony pockets. However, its elimination should improve the clinical status of periodontitis.

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